

THE EFFECT OF INTERACTIONS BETWEEN CRIMINAL HISTORY, AGE, RACE,
GENDER, AND EMPLOYMENT ON OFFENDER RECIDIVISM

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Abstract

Previous studies describing the relationship between offender employment and recidivism rates have typically not reported results for each separate demographic, risk, and employment category. Results from reports that did provide separate effect measures indicate that there are possible differences in recidivism rates for employed and unemployed offenders in different age, gender, race, and risk categories. When results were separated, the separation was single category, male, female, young, old, etc. This study provides an analysis of the relationship between employment and recidivism rate for each separate demographic and risk category. The results show marked differences in the relationship between employment and recidivism for the offenders in the various demographic and risk categories. Small numbers in some categories may be skewing the results, so further investigation is needed to determine whether the differences found are a universal phenomenon and, if so, why there are differences in the protective effects of employment between various groups of offenders.

The Effect of Interactions Between Criminal History, Age, Race, Gender, and Employment on Offender Recidivism

There has been a debate in the criminology literature about the relationship between employment and recidivism (Cohen, & Vila, 1996). Sampson and Laub (1990; 1993), using data originally collected by the Gluecks (1950; 1968), found evidence that indicates that ex-offenders are less likely to recidivate when employed. Sampson and Laub suggest that offenders who get a stable job experience a turning point in their offending trajectory because of informal social control that is exerted by coworkers on the offender. Hirschi and Gottfredson (1995) argued that offenders who are employed have higher levels of self-control and recidivate less because of their greater self-control. They attribute apparent changes in offending to “self selection and statistical regression” (p. 137). They suggest that offenders with low self-control would not be able to get and hold a job and would not benefit from employment due to their low self-control.

Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990) have suggested that the only way to truly determine whether employment reduces recidivism rates is to randomly assign ex-offenders to employment or a control group. Several studies have attempted to create random assignment of ex-offenders to employment. The evidence as to the efficacy of employment as a treatment option has not been strong. The study results have been quite varied and many of the studies examining whether assignment to employment is effective in reducing recidivism have methodological deficits that call the results into question (Wilson, Gallagher, and MacKenzie, 2000), or indicate that employment programs do not reduce recidivism (Visher, Winterfield, & Coggeshall, 2005).

While the treatment literature has shown inconsistent or inconclusive results, evidence is strong that employment status and employability are excellent predictors of recidivism for white male offenders. A meta-analysis of assessment studies done by Jones (2005) found that employment factors had a significant correlation with recidivism ($r_m = .12$). The strongest

predictors of recidivism were employment history and employment needs at discharge, followed by employment status at intake, financial problems, and various indicators of problems with education.

The connection between employment and recidivism for females, non-white offenders, and offenders of different age groups and risk levels is not as clear. Jones reports that the assessment studies he analyzed, as part of a meta-analysis, had inconsistencies in the relationship between employment and recidivism for female and native offenders. Bonta, Pang, and Wallace-Capretta (1995) found no connection between employment measures and recidivism rates for female offenders. Saylor and Gaes (1996) reported significant variation in the association between employment program participation and recidivism rates for offenders who varied by age, race, gender, and criminal propensity. Uggen (2000) found that age differences determined whether offenders experienced a protective effect from employment.

The inconsistencies in the results from existing research suggest that the relationship between employment and recidivism may vary substantially by age, race, gender, and risk level, and the inconclusive results found by treatment researchers are due to a failure on the part of researchers to separate the offenders by demographic category and risk level. If there are factors related to age, gender, race, and risk level that are related to the effectiveness of employment as a protective factor in reducing recidivism, the results will differ for offenders in those demographic categories. Although there is a growing recognition from feminist criminologists that there is a need for increased attention to race, class, and gender differences (Burgess-Proctor, 2006), it does not appear that much previous research has been done to determine whether the association between employment and recidivism rate varies by demographic category and offender risk level.

This study fills a gap in the offender employment research literature by providing an examination of the interaction between age, race, gender, criminal history, employment, and recidivism. Following a review of the literature, several hypotheses will be generated, and then an offender assessment dataset from a Midwest community corrections department will be analyzed to determine whether there are differences in the effect of employment on recidivism rates for various groups of offenders.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The use of employment to facilitate the rehabilitation of probationers began 150 years ago with the efforts of John Augustus (Panzarella, 2002). Augustus sat in a courtroom and when he saw someone coming to trial that he felt could be “reformed”, waited until the offender was convicted, and then asked the judge if he could post the offender’s bail and have a chance to work with the offender for one month before sentence was passed. After the month was up, the judge would usually be impressed with the reformation and let the offender go with a minimal fine. Augustus reputedly tried to make sure each offender was employed immediately after the offender was placed in his care. The activities of John Augustus became the model for the modern practice of probation.

Efforts to increase the level of employment for ex-offenders continue to be popular in more recent times. The state and federal correctional systems offer vocational training in over half of the correctional facilities, and offer employment-counseling services in almost two-thirds of facilities (Stephan, & Karberg, 2003). Education programs, which would theoretically lead to better jobs upon release, are also widely implemented in correctional facilities. Petersilia (2003) asserts “Employment remains one of the most important vehicles for hastening offender reintegration and desistance from crime ...”.

While, on the surface, efforts to enhance offender employment have intuitive appeal, they are not without detractors. Heckman (1994) argues that supported employment and employment-training programs are not cost effective, and money spent on these programs would be better spent elsewhere.

The mixed and inconclusive results found in studies of the relationship between employment and recidivism stem, in part, from difficulty determining whether the effects of employment are due to previous differences in likelihood to reoffend or whether they are due to efforts to enhance employment options. Wilson, Gallagher, and MacKenzie (2000) performed a meta-analytic study of 33 employment studies and found that offenders who participated in employment programs had a 39% average recidivism rate compared to a 50% rate for offenders in the control groups, suggesting some benefit. They could not determine whether the results were due to real effects or to exogenous factors such as propensity to offend, as suggested by Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990), because there were large differences in outcome between programs, and deficiencies in study designs lead to inconclusive results. They tried to determine whether there were differences between program outcomes by risk level, and found that the low risk subjects showed a larger difference in the differential for offending between the employed and unemployed, but the difference was still not significant when possible random factors were added to the model.

Studies of community based employment programs show that such programs have no overall effect in reducing recidivism. Visher, Winterfield, and Coggeshall (2005) analyzed a number of community based employment programs and found that there was only one study (Uggen, 2000) that showed a definitive positive effect for an employment program in reducing recidivism and that was only for offenders 27 and older.

Not all studies show null results when comparing employment with recidivism. Saylor and Gaes (1996), in an employment program study cited by Wilson et. al. as having one of the strongest methodological designs, found that there was a significant association between participation in supported employment or vocational training programs and a reduction in recidivism. The results varied substantially by race, gender, age, criminal history, and education level however. They could find no significant relationship between employment and recidivism for female offenders, which they attributed to low sample size. A negative relationship between employment program participation and recidivism was found for minorities and younger offenders. Education and risk levels had mixed effects on program outcome.

Results from other studies show mixed associations between employment and crime. Sampson (1987), analyzing data from 171 U.S. cities in 1980, compared the effects of joblessness on black male violence and found no significant direct effects between employment and violence, but did find that joblessness had a significant impact on family disruption, which in turn was significantly related to black male violence. Thornberry and Christenson (1984), analyzing data from a 10% sample of the Philadelphia birth cohort (Wolfgang et. al., 1972), found that unemployment at time one had a weak relationship to criminal involvement in the subsequent year (.126, $p < .10$) for subjects measured at 21 and again at 22. When blacks and whites were analyzed separately, the relationships (.078, .193) in the 21-22 age range did not reach significance, but the differences in the magnitudes of the correlation coefficients suggest differences between groups in the association between employment and recidivism. The relationship between unemployment and criminal involvement increased substantially in subsequent years (22-23, 23-24), which was interpreted as indicating that long term unemployment and criminal involvement have reciprocal effects on each other.

Theoretical Considerations

There are several theoretical models that attempt to explain the effects of employment and unemployment on criminal behavior. The relationship between each theory and employment will each be discussed.

Rational Choice Theories. Rational choice theorists Cornish and Clark (1986) posit that the offender is a reasoning actor and suggest that crime occurs after the offender weighs the benefits of crime against the risks of getting caught. Ehrlich (1973) suggested that crime could be seen as a type of employment that fills the need for resources much as a job does for others.

Opportunity theorists Cohen and Felson (1979) emphasize a rational choice model of offending which indicates that predatory offending occurs when a suitable target, a capable and motivated offender with criminal inclinations, and a lack of a capable guardian are present. It is possible that employment could increase opportunity for crime by placing the person in situations where crime is more likely, such as late at night when few people are present.

Social Control and Stake in Conformity Theories. Social control theorists argue that crime is a result of weak bonds to society (Hirschi, 1969). Employment can build bonds to society through social bonding to coworkers. Sampson and Laub (1993) found that employment often had a protective effect for offenders and could create apparent turning points in the criminal trajectory. They posit that this is due to informal social control in the workplace. Steinberg and Dornbusch (1991) suggest that there may be negative consequences of employment for adolescents because employment can increase bonding to deviant peers and reduce bonding to parents. Stake in Conformity Theorists (Toby, 1957) suggest that crime is inversely related to the level of participation in society, such as being employed, that offenders have in legitimate society.

Strain Theories. The strain theory of crime was developed by Merton (1938), Cohen (1955), and Cloward and Ohlin (1960). Merton (1938) theorized that there are five ways that people can react to the strain that results from blocked goals: conformity, innovation, ritualism, retreatism, and rebellion. Criminal behavior results from innovation or rebellion in a response to strain. Innovation results in crime when people invent new ways to achieve success, such as dealing drugs. Rebellion results in crime when people reject society's goals and methods of attaining those goals. Cloward (1959) suggests that differential opportunity structures exist in society that lead to differences between classes in the level of opportunity to attain desired goals. It is suggested that if more opportunities, i.e. employment options, were available to lower class individuals, their likelihood of committing crimes would be reduced. Farnworth and Lieber (1989) found that the propositions of strain theory were only supported when both financial goals and educational attainment goals were thwarted. Agnew (1992) reworked strain theory, suggesting that strain results when legitimate avenues to positively valued goals such as monetary success or middle class status are blocked. He suggests that strain occurs when the actual level of achievement is less than the desired level of achievement.

Self-Control Theory. Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990) suggest that criminal behavior results from low self-control. People who have low self-control "tend to be impulsive, insensitive, physical (as opposed to mental), risk-taking, short-sighted, and non-verbal" (p. 90). They claim that since people normally age out of crime as they get older, reductions in criminal behavior are the result of aging effects rather than environmental factors. People who get a job and stop committing crimes have higher levels of self-control than people who keep committing crimes.

Hypotheses

The previous research on offending suggests the following hypotheses,

- 1) Employment will have a protective effect for the average offender.
- 2) Employment will have no protective effect for offenders with an extensive criminal history.
- 3) Employment will have a protective effect for offenders who are 27 or older and no effect for younger offenders.
- 4) Employment will have no protective effect for female offenders.
- 5) Employment will have no protective effect for minority offenders.
- 6) Interaction effects between age, gender, race, and employment status will be additive.

METHODS

Participants and Data Sources

The subjects used in this study were 3190 offenders who were placed on probation in a Midwestern County between 2002 and 2006. Corrections officials interviewed the offenders about various facets of their local life circumstances, and also collected data about previous convictions, current offenses, birthdates, gender, etc. Arrest and conviction data was collected, as well as probation violation data, for the time periods before and after the interviews. The data sources used in this study consisted of the interview records, Bureau of Criminal Apprehension (BCA) arrest and conviction records, and Court Services parole violation records resulting in a commitment to prison.

Sample selection. To avoid undercounting conviction and parole violations, only data from interviews done from 2002 through 2004 were used in the study phase. This allowed for the analysis of 12-month recidivism rates with an additional year from the end of the study period for any arrests to be processed as convictions and be entered into the BCA database. It is assumed that most violations come to trial and turn into convictions within 1 year after the violation date. The sample in this study used consists of the interview records of all of the offenders with two assessments completed before 2005.

Sample demographic data. The sample consisted of 3190 offenders with a mean age of 32.57. 81% of the sample was male. The racial distribution was 82% white and 18% other races (13% black; 2% Asian; 3% Native American).

Sample Risk Level. The risk levels of the offenders used in this study were assessed using the Level of Service Inventory-Revised (LSI-R; Andrews and Bonta, 1995). A set of national norms for the LSI-R have been established using seven samples totaling 23,271 corrections and prison offenders from seven U.S. jurisdictions (Andrews and Bonta, 2003). The LSI-R scores for the offenders analyzed in this study were found to be almost identical to the national averages for other offenders in community corrections.

Figure 1

LSI-R Risk Level of Offender Sample Compared with National Prison and Corrections Norms

Data Variables

The dependent variable used in this study, called Violation, was coded a one if either a felony arrest leading to conviction or a probation violation leading to incarceration occurred within one year of the assessment. While a probation violation is not as serious as a felony arrest, there was no way to determine whether the offender would have offended if he or she had

not been sent to prison for the probation violation. The independent variables used in this study were History, which was coded as a zero if the total number of offenses (previous + current) was less than or equal to 3, and coded a one if the total number of offenses was over 4; Under27, which was coded a one for offenders 26 and younger at assessment completion and a zero for offenders 27 and older; Male, which was coded as a one for males and a zero for females; White, which was coded as a one for white offenders and a zero for all other races; and Employed, which was coded as a one for employed and a zero for unemployed.

Two, three and four way interaction terms were created by cross multiplying the five terms used in the base model. This resulted in the following interaction variables; two way: HistoryXUnder27, HistoryXWhite, HistoryXMale, HistoryXEmployed, Under27XWhite, Under27Xmale, Under27Xemployed, WhiteXMale, WhiteXEmployed, MaleXEmployed; three way: HistoryXUnder27XWhite, HistoryXUnder27Xmale, HistoryXUnder27Xemployed, HistoryXWhiteXMale, HistoryXWhiteXEmployed, HistoryXMaleXEmployed, Under27XwhiteXMale, Under27XwhiteXEmployed, Under27XmaleXEmployed, WhiteXMaleXEmployed; and four way: HistoryXUnder27XwhiteXMale, HistoryXUnder27XwhiteXEmployed, HistoryXUnder27XmaleXEmployed, HistoryXWhiteXMaleXEmployed, and Under27XwhiteXMaleXEmployed

To control for other possible factors that might account for any results found, the LSI-R subscale scores Financial_Problems, Family_Marital, Accommodation, Leisure_Recreation, Companions, Alcohol_Drug, Emotional_Personal, and Attitude_Orientation were used without modification. The value of the q11 score (Are you employed?) was subtracted from the Education_Employment subscale score and the rest of the subscale score was used for the Education_Employment variable. A variable called Institution, which included LSI-R questions

q07, q08, q09, and q10, was created to reflect any risk factors due to prior arrest history of institutional misconduct.

Equipment

The data were analyzed using SPSS 13 for Windows, and Microsoft Excel.

Research Design

This study is a retrospective analysis of secondary data collected by others. The independent variables were collected in the routine performance of duties by probation officers. The data measuring the dependent variable, conviction and/or probation violation, were collected by the court system.

Procedure

A logistic regression was performed because of the dichotomous nature of the dependent variable. Logistic regression is used in statistics to determine the probability of occurrence of the dependent variable when the dependent variable is dichotomous. The formula used to determine the probability Y in terms of independent variables X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i is $Y = 1/(1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_i X_i)})$. The value of Y when all values of X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i are zero, gives the intercept of Y , which is calculated as $Y = 1/(1 + e^{-(\beta_0)})$.

When interaction terms are used in logistic regression, the cross products of the independent variables are added to the model. The formula for a three way interaction model with independent variables X_1, X_2 , and X_3 would become

$$Y = 1/(1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_{12} X_1 X_2 + \beta_{13} X_1 X_3 + \beta_{23} X_2 X_3 + \beta_{123} X_1 X_2 X_3)}).$$

A graphical plot to explain the concept of interaction terms is shown in Figure 2. The Logistic Regression terms A, B, and C, have two-way interaction terms $A \times B$, $A \times C$, and $B \times C$, and a three-way interaction term $A \times B \times C$. The terms may be interpreted by the area available in the intersection of the variables, which represents the amount of explanation each term provides. In the model shown, A and C are significant and B is not because all of the explanatory power is used in the interaction terms. $A \times B$, and $A \times C$ are significant and $B \times C$ is not because no area is left that is not included in the higher order interaction term $A \times B \times C$. $A \times B \times C$ is significant because the area in the intersection of all three variables is significant.

Jackard (2001), citing Kleinbaum (1992), stresses the importance of using hierarchically well formulated models when doing interaction analysis in logistic regression. In a hierarchically well formulated model, all lower order interaction terms must be included in the model if they are used in a higher order term. For instance if $AxBxC$ is used in the model, AxB , AxC , and BxC must also be included in the model.

The interpretation of interaction effects is not as simple as in ordinary logistic regression, where the sign and magnitude of the logistic regression coefficients may be observed to determine the relative contribution of each independent variable. When using interaction terms, all of the terms that use a particular variable must be added together to determine the overall effect (Ai, & Norton, 2003). Another method that may be used to determine the magnitude of the interaction effect is to plot the values of Y for various values of the independent variables (Rosnow, & Rosenthal, 1989).

The main effect variables, History, Under27, White, Male, and Employed, were used in Model 1. Interaction terms were added in subsequent steps in the model, two-way interactions in Model 2, three-way interactions in Model 3, and four way interactions-in Model 4. The process was repeated with the LSI-R subscale scores included in Model 5 at step two, and two-way interactions in Model 6, three-way interactions in Model 7, and four way interactions-in Model 8. In Model 9, all of the insignificant LSI-R terms and insignificant four-way interaction terms were removed.

Probability values were calculated using a custom Excel spreadsheet. The mean LSI-R values in Appendix 1 were used to calculate probabilities for models that included LSI-R variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

The numbers of offenders per demographic and risk category were calculated to insure that there were enough data points in each cell for an accurate analysis. The results are tabulated in Table 1 and displayed in Figure 3. The minimum number of offenders in any cell was 5.

The results indicate that employment has a significant overall protective effect in reducing recidivism for both high offense and low offense offenders, supporting Hypothesis 1: *Employment will have a protective effect for the average offender*. Hypothesis 2: *Employment will have no protective effect for offenders with an extensive criminal history*, was partially supported, as high offense white offenders did receive a protective effect from employment, and high offense non-white offenders did not. Hypothesis 3: *Employment will have a protective effect for offenders who are 27 or older and no effect for younger offenders*, was partially supported, as some younger offenders, young white males, and young low-risk non-white males, received a significant protective effect from employment. Hypothesis 4: *Employment will have no protective effect for female offenders*, appears to be supported by the data. Hypothesis 5: *Employment will have no protective effect for minority offenders*, has a split result. Low risk non-white male offenders experience a substantial protective effect, while other non-white groups have minimal, or negative effects.

These results suggest that individual demographic groupings such as age, are not adequate as controls for differences in the protective effects of employment. The differences between groups vary substantially from one demographic group to another by all variables, age, race, and gender, as well as employment status.

Table 1

Mean New Violation Rate, and Number of Offenders per Age, Race, and Gender Category by Offense History and Employment Status

	Low Offense				High Offense			
	Employed Mean	Unemployed n	Unemployed Mean	Difference n	Employed Mean	Unemployed n	Unemployed Mean	Difference n
Under 27 White Male	.18	302	.35	137 .17***	.31	240	.44	196 .14**
Under 27 White Female	.14	76	.18	51 .03	.35	37	.47	32 .12
Older White Male	.11	280	.17	95 .05	.25	520	.34	321 .10*
Older White Female	.10	102	.18	55 .08	.12	81	.27	79 .14*
Under 27 Non-White Male	.21	24	.56	34 .35**	.48	21	.59	82 .11
Under 27 Non-White Female	.29	7	.00	7 -.29	.40	5	.45	11 .05
Older Non-White Male	.11	47	.55	22 .44***	.41	105	.49	154 .08
Older Non-White Female	.20	15	.17	12 -.03	.41	17	.48	23 .07
Totals	.14	853	.28	413 .14***	1026	.28	898	.41 .13***

* p<.05; ** p<.01; *** p<.001

Figure 3

Mean New Violation Rate, and Number of Offenders per Age, Race, and Gender Category by Offense History and Employment Status

Logistic Regression Base Model

The logistic regression base model was calculated using History, Under 27, White, Male, and Employed as independent variables, and Violation as the dependent variable. The base model is shown in Table 2. All regression coefficients are significant at the $p < .001$ level with the exception of Male, which is significant at the $p < .01$ level. The number of total offenses is the most significant predictor of new violations. The B coefficients are in the expected direction, with higher offenses count, lower age, and male gender all associated with higher likelihood of a new violation. Being white or employed both are associated with a reduction in the likelihood of new violation.

Table 2

Logistic Regression Coefficients for Base Model Predicting New Violation Within One Year

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95.0% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
History	0.749	0.092	66.561	1	0.000	2.115	1.767	2.532
Under27	0.480	0.086	31.482	1	0.000	1.616	1.366	1.910
White	-0.669	0.100	44.782	1	0.000	0.512	0.421	0.623
Male	0.309	0.112	7.577	1	0.006	1.362	1.093	1.696
Employed	-0.561	0.084	44.883	1	0.000	0.571	0.484	0.672
Constant	-1.046	0.149	48.993	1	0.000	0.351		

-2 Log likelihood: 3531.807, Cox & Snell R Square: .074, Nagelkerke R Square, .107

The probability of new offense was calculated for each of the values of History, Under27, White, Male, and Employed and tabulated in Table 3. Note that there is a 600% difference in likelihood for offending between an employed older white female ($p = .09$) and an unemployed non-white male ($p = .62$).

Table 3

Probability of New Violation Within One-Year Calculated from Base Model

	Employed	Unemployed		Employed	Unemployed	
	Low Offense	High Offense	Difference	Low Offense	High Offense	Difference
Under 27 White Male	.18	.28	.10	.32	.46	.13
Under 27 White Female	.14	.23	.08	.26	.38	.12
Older White Male	.12	.20	.07	.23	.34	.11
Older White Female	.09	.15	.06	.18	.28	.10
Under 27 Non-White Male	.31	.44	.13	.48	.62	.14
Under 27 Non-White Female	.24	.36	.12	.41	.55	.14
Older Non-White Male	.21	.32	.11	.37	.50	.14
Older Non-White Female	.17	.26	.09	.30	.43	.13

The output from Table 3 was charted and placed in Figure 4. The plot represents a substantial simplification of the data, indicating the effects of sample homogenization.

Figure 4

Probability of New Violation Within One Year Calculated from Base Model

Logistic Regression: Base Model with LSI-R

The second step in the logistic regression model was to add the LSI-R subscale scores to the model. The results are shown in Table 3 below. History, Under27, and White remained significant. Male and Employed variables became insignificant. Institution, and Attitude_Orientation were significant at the $p < .001$ level, Accommodation was significant at the $p < .05$ level, and the rest of the LSI-R subscale variables were not significant factors in the model. The calculated probabilities reveal that adding the LSI-R factors to the model results in substantially lower differences in probability of new violation for high offense offenders and a smaller protective effect for employment.

Table 4

Logistic Regression Coefficients for Base Model Plus LSI-R Subscale Scores
Predicting New Violation Within One Year

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95.0% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
History	0.444	0.101	19.377	1	0.000	1.559	1.280	1.901
Under27	0.408	0.091	19.957	1	0.000	1.504	1.258	1.799
White	-0.486	0.105	21.384	1	0.000	0.615	0.501	0.756
Male	0.188	0.120	2.473	1	0.116	1.207	0.955	1.526
Employed	-0.208	0.135	2.387	1	0.122	0.812	0.624	1.057
Institution	0.187	0.050	14.162	1	0.000	1.206	1.094	1.330
Education_Employment	0.033	0.029	1.267	1	0.260	1.034	0.976	1.095
Financial_Problems	-0.046	0.070	0.419	1	0.517	0.955	0.832	1.097
Family_Marital	0.072	0.040	3.239	1	0.072	1.074	0.994	1.162
Accomodation	0.111	0.049	5.185	1	0.023	1.117	1.016	1.228
Leisure_Recreation	0.020	0.061	0.106	1	0.745	1.020	0.905	1.149
Companions	0.059	0.039	2.243	1	0.134	1.060	0.982	1.145
Alcohol_Drug	0.002	0.017	0.010	1	0.921	1.002	0.969	1.035
Emotional_Personal	-0.055	0.034	2.552	1	0.110	0.946	0.885	1.013
Attitude_Orientation	0.159	0.033	22.837	1	0.000	1.173	1.099	1.252
Constant	-1.838	0.234	61.550	1	0.000	0.159		

-2 Log likelihood: 3434.706, Cox & Snell R Square: .102, Nagelkerke R Square: .147

Logistic Regression Interaction Models

The logistic regression models predicting violation were set up with History, Under27, White, Male, and Employed as the first step. Then, the two, three, and four way interaction models were run without the LSI-R subscales. The base model was run with the LSI-R subscales, and then the two, three, and four way interaction models were run with the LSI-R subscales. Finally, a model was run without the insignificant LSI-R subscales and insignificant four-way interaction terms. The insignificant two-way and three-way interaction terms were left in the final model to preserve the hierarchal model assumptions. All of the logistic regression models were placed in Table 5. The probabilities of recidivism for each demographic and risk category were calculated using the LSI-R sample means for each demographic category and placed in Table 6. The mean LSI-R subscale values used for calculating the probabilities are shown in Appendix 1 for reference. The probabilities of recidivism for employed and unemployed offenders were plotted for each demographic and risk category in Figure 5. The probabilities of recidivism for employed and unemployed offenders were plotted for low offense offenders in Figure 6, and for high offense offenders in Figure 7.

Table 5

Logistic Regression Models Predicting New Violation Within One Year

Terms	Base Model	2 Way	3 Way	4 Way	Base Model W-LSI-R	2 Way W-LSI-R	3 Way W-LSI-R	4 Way W-LSI-R	Significant Terms Only
History	.749*** (.092)	.809** (.300)	.934 (.600)	1.687 (.874)	.444*** (.101)	.298 (.310)	.404 (.613)	1.134 (.883)	1.254 (.853)
Under27	.480*** (.086)	.449 (.301)	-1.109 (.743)	-1.761 (1.627)	.408*** (.091)	.311 (.309)	-1.063 (.755)	-1.723 (1.661)	-1.190 (.784)
White	-.669*** (.100)	-.700* (.332)	-.443 (.606)	.259 (.848)	-.486*** (.105)	-.525 (.338)	-.148 (.616)	.481 (.853)	.536 (.826)
Male	.309** (.112)	.576a (.326)	1.020a (.609)	1.958* (.879)	.188 (.120)	.431 (.335)	.872 (.623)	1.772* (.890)	1.706* (.849)
Employed	-.561*** (.084)	-.680* (.298)	-.367 (.649)	.435 (.974)	-.208 (.135)	-.411 (.319)	-.064 (.667)	.695 (.986)	.900 (.932)
Institution					.187*** (.050)	.190*** (.050)	.189*** (.050)	.189*** (.050)	.199*** (.048)
Education_Employment					.033 (.029)	.031 (.030)	.028 (.030)	.028 (.030)	
Financial_Problems					-.046 (.070)	-.047 (.071)	-.044 (.071)	-.045 (.071)	
Family_Marital					.072a (.040)	.071a (.040)	.069a (.040)	.068a (.040)	.063a (.038)
Accomodation					.111* (.049)	.113* (.049)	.114* (.049)	.114* (.049)	.125** (.048)
Leisure_Recreation					.020 (.061)	.019 (.061)	.024 (.061)	.023 (.061)	
Companions					.059 (.039)	.059 (.039)	.059 (.039)	.055 (.039)	
Alcohol_Drug					.002 (.017)	.002 (.017)	.000 (.017)	.000 (.017)	
Emotional_Personal					-.055 (.034)	-.057a (.035)	-.057 (.035)	-.055 (.035)	
Attitude_Orientation					.159*** (.033)	.159*** (.033)	.159*** (.034)	.160*** (.034)	.169*** (.032)

Table 5 (Continued)

Logistic Regression Models Predicting New Violation Within One Year

Terms	Base Model	2 Way	3 Way	4 Way	Base Model W-LSI-R	2 Way W-LSI-R	3 Way W-LSI-R	4 Way W-LSI-R	Significant Terms Only
HistoryXUnder27		-.089 (.186)	.977 (.628)	1.555 (1.607)		.050 (.190)	1.051a (.638)	1.590 (1.639)	1.103a (.646)
HistoryXWhite		-.050 (.235)	-.255 (.637)	-1.237 (.958)		.064 (.239)	-.211 (.647)	-1.114 (.967)	-1.182 (.922)
HistoryXMale		-.213 (.237)	-.771 (.623)	-1.964* (.968)		-.158 (.240)	-.625 (.634)	-1.787a (.980)	-1.656a (.925)
HistoryXEmployed		.358a (.187)	.376 (.599)	-.791 (1.126)		.356a (.191)	.460 (.609)	-.692 (1.141)	-1.087 (1.089)
Under27XWhite		.218 (.217)	1.126 (.710)	1.672 (1.620)		.202 (.222)	.856 (.721)	1.484 (1.653)	1.039 (.738)
Under27XMale		-.039 (.233)	1.561* (.699)	1.753 (1.618)		-.096 (.237)	1.389a (.711)	1.599 (1.651)	1.520* (.721)
Under27XEmployed		-.109 (.176)	.768 (.623)	1.999 (1.564)		-.036 (.181)	.766 (.633)	1.921 (1.597)	.849 (.639)
WhiteXMale		-.050 (.277)	-.844 (.644)	-2.091* (.967)		-.102 (.283)	-.917 (.655)	-2.060* (.977)	-1.854* (.912)
WhiteXEmployed		.072 (.207)	-.169 (.654)	-1.198 (1.063)		.002 (.213)	-.379 (.664)	-1.296 (1.071)	-1.591 (1.001)
MaleXEmployed		-.171 (.226)	-1.307* (.634)	-2.830* (1.125)		-.053 (.230)	-1.192a (.644)	-2.650* (1.137)	-2.579* (1.046)

Table 5 (Continued)

Logistic Regression Models Predicting New Violation Within One Year

Terms	Base Model	2 Way	3 Way	4 Way	Base Model W-LSI-R	2 Way W-LSI-R	3 Way W-LSI-R	4 Way W-LSI-R	Significant Terms Only
HistoryXUnder27XWhite			-.124 (.504)	-.536 (1.577)			.050 (.513)	-.432 (1.609)	-.063 (.521)
HistoryXUnder27XMale			-1.112* (.490)	-1.134 (1.583)			-1.127* (.497)	-1.115 (1.613)	-1.106* (.496)
HistoryXUnder27XEmployed			-.014 (.386)	-1.623 (1.324)			-.144 (.393)	-1.502 (1.348)	-.131 (.393)
HistoryXWhiteXMale			.776 (.633)	2.394* (1.073)			.730 (.642)	2.235* (1.087)	1.965* (.999)
HistoryXWhiteXEmployed			-.926a (.497)	.646 (1.245)			-.836a (.507)	.614 (1.261)	1.024 (1.187)
HistoryXMaleXEmployed			.870a (.482)	2.885* (1.263)			.752 (.489)	2.732* (1.281)	2.699* (1.209)
Under27XWhiteXMale			-.764 (.622)	-.663 (1.600)			-.656 (.631)	-.678 (1.632)	-.742 (.634)
Under27XWhiteXEmployed			-.303 (.467)	-1.423 (1.514)			-.187 (.478)	-1.353 (1.547)	-.261 (.483)
Under27XMaleXEmployed			-.717 (.480)	-1.100 (1.473)			-.645 (.488)	-.973 (1.503)	-.698 (.486)
WhiteXMaleXEmployed			1.188* (.581)	3.165** (1.226)			1.233* (.590)	3.037** (1.239)	2.866* (1.116)

Table 5 (Continued)

Logistic Regression Models Predicting New Violation Within One Year

Terms	Base Model	2 Way	3 Way	4 Way	Base Model W-LSI-R	2 Way W-LSI-R	3 Way W-LSI-R	4 Way W-LSI-R	Significant Terms Only
HistoryXUnder27X WhiteXMale				-.383 (1.526)				-.270 (1.554)	
HistoryXUnder27X WhiteXEmployed				1.416 (1.075)				1.359 (1.095)	
HistoryXUnder27X MaleXEmployed				.535 (1.004)				.278 (1.020)	
HistoryXWhiteX MaleXEmployed				-2.701* (1.383)				-2.515a (1.403)	-2.358a (1.319)
Under27XWhiteX MaleXEmployed				.011 (1.362)				.129 (1.393)	
Constant	-1.046*** (.149)	-1.122*** (.347)	-1.183 (.560)	-1.738* (.784)	-1.838*** (.234)	-1.764*** (.394)	-1.867** (.600)	-2.385** (.810)	-2.443** (.776)
-2 Log likelihood	3538.800	3531.807	3512.377	3506.747	3434.706	3429.383	3412.314	3414.022	3415.921
Cox & Snell R Square	.072	.074	.080	.081	.102	.103	.108	.108	.107
Nagelkerke R Square	.104	.107	.115	.117	.147	.149	.156	.155	.154

Table 6

Probability Calculations from Regression Model With Significant LSI-R and Four-way Interaction Terms Predicting New Violation Within One Year

	Low Offense			High Offense		
	Employed	Unemployed	Difference	Employed	Unemployed	Difference
Under 27 White Male	.17	.34	.16	.30	.45	.15
Under 27 White Female	.15	.17	.02	.34	.47	.13
Older White Male	.11	.17	.07	.24	.31	.07
Older White Female	.09	.18	.09	.12	.26	.14
Under 27 Non-White Male	.18	.59	.41	.51	.57	.06
Under 27 Non-White Female	.19	.04	-.15	.49	.44	-.05
Older Non-White Male	.12	.50	.38	.40	.49	.09
Older Non-White Female	.24	.14	-.10	.38	.48	.10

Figure 5

Plot of Probability Calculations Regression Model With Significant LSI-R and Four-way Interaction Terms Predicting New Violation Within One Year

Figure 5

Plot of Probability Calculations Regression Model With Significant LSI-R and Four-way Interaction Terms Predicting New Violation Within One Year (Low Offense Offenders Only)

Figure 7

Plot of Probability Calculations Regression Model With Significant LSI-R and Four-way Interaction Terms Predicting New Violation Within One Year (High Offense Offenders Only)

The only significant term left in the base model after the interaction terms were calculated was the Male term. This suggests that there was some portion of the recidivism rate attributable to the Gender variable that was independent of the interaction terms. LSI-R subscale items Institution, Family_Marital, Accomodation, and Attitude_Orientation were all significant in the final model, indicating that these variables are related to recidivism, independent of the other factors. HistoryXUnder27, HistoryXMale, Under27Xmale, WhiteXMale, and MaleXEmployed were significant in the two-way interaction terms. HistoryXUnder27XMale, HistoryXWhiteXMale, HistoryXMaleXEmployed, and WhiteXMaleXEmployed were significant in the three-way interaction terms. HistoryXWhiteXMaleXEmployed was significant in the four way interaction terms.

The pattern in the interaction terms suggests that age is more important in the two-way interactions than in higher order interactions. The Male variable interacts with all of the other variables, suggesting that gender is an important factor in employment. This confirms previous research results. History and race also show a fairly consistent presence in the interaction terms.

The plots in Figure 6 indicate that there is little difference in the probability of arrest for any low offense employed demographic group. Demographic category makes a significant difference for the low offense unemployed offenders, showing substantial interaction effects. The plots in Figure 7 show that there are fewer interaction effects for high offense offenders but the difference in probability of new offense within one year varies substantially by demographic category for both employed and unemployed offenders.

The plot in Figure 5 reveals a striking difference between low offense non-white males and high offense non-white males in the relationship between employment status and recidivism. Low offense non-white males have one of the greatest differentials between new offense levels

based on employment status. High offense non-white males have one of the lowest differences in new offenses based on employment status. It is also noteworthy that the non-white females had higher new offense rates in the employed categories than the unemployed categories. The plot also shows that low risk white females receive little benefit from employment.

A test of the accuracy of calculations was done to determine whether the final logistic regression model provided an accurate fit to the data, and whether the mean LSI-R subscale means or the individual category LSI-R means provided a better fit. The LSI-R means, minimum values, and maximum values were also calculated to show whether the results from the model were consistent with the risk scores assigned to the offenders. The data was rank ordered on the first column. The results were placed in Table 7, and plotted in Figure 8.

From the results, it appears that the probabilities calculated in column 1 using the individual category LSI-R subscale means provide a better fit to the category mean new offense rates in column 3 than the probabilities in column 2 that were calculated using the mean LSI-R subscale means. The slope of the model plots are steeper than the LSI-R slopes, which could be a result of scaling, or it could suggest that demographic interactions with employment provide additional information in addition to the information provided by the LSI-R score. There does appear to be a better fit on the low end than the high end of the scale. The higher probability of new offenses on the high end may simply be a function of the heavy weighting towards non-white offenders, which is a known problem with this dataset.

Table 7

Probability Calculations from Regression Model With Significant LSI-R and Four-way Interaction Terms Predicting New Violation Within One Year Using Individual LSI-R Means, Probability Using Mean LSI-R Means, Mean Offense, Mean LSI-R, Maximum LSI-R, and Minimum LSI-R Rank Ordered on Logistic Regression Probability

	Model Probability	Mean Prob.	Mean Offense	Mean LSI-R	Min. LSI-R	Max. LSI-R
Unemployed Low Offense Under 27 Non-White Female	4	5	0	21	14	31
Employed Low Offense Older White Female	9	13	10	12	1	32
Employed Low Offense Older White Male	11	14	11	12	1	33
Employed Low Offense Older Non-White Male	12	15	11	11	2	27
Employed High Offense Older White Female	12	13	12	20	7	42
Unemployed Low Offense Older Non-White Female	14	14	17	26	16	35
Employed Low Offense Under 27 White Female	15	18	14	14	1	35
Unemployed Low Offense Under 27 White Female	17	20	18	22	9	40
Employed Low Offense Under 27 White Male	17	22	18	13	1	35
Unemployed Low Offense Older White Male	17	20	17	22	6	35
Employed Low Offense Under 27 Non-White Male	18	22	21	13	2	33
Unemployed Low Offense Older White Female	18	22	18	22	10	35
Employed Low Offense Under 27 Non-White Female	19	23	29	16	8	24
Employed Low Offense Older Non-White Female	24	29	20	13	4	22
Employed High Offense Older White Male	24	24	25	20	6	40
Unemployed High Offense Older White Female	26	23	27	30	10	46
Employed High Offense Under 27 White Male	30	30	31	21	4	41
Unemployed High Offense Older White Male	31	26	34	30	14	47
Unemployed Low Offense Under 27 White Male	34	32	35	26	6	45
Employed High Offense Under 27 White Female	34	36	35	21	7	31
Employed High Offense Older Non-White Female	38	33	41	26	12	40
Employed High Offense Older Non-White Male	40	37	41	23	8	47
Unemployed High Offense Under 27 Non-White Female	44	35	45	32	22	47
Unemployed High Offense Under 27 White Male	45	39	44	31	13	47
Unemployed High Offense Under 27 White Female	47	43	47	29	17	44
Unemployed High Offense Older Non-White Female	48	37	48	34	17	48
Unemployed High Offense Older Non-White Male	49	38	49	32	15	47
Employed High Offense Under 27 Non-White Female	49	48	40	23	11	38
Unemployed Low Offense Older Non-White Male	50	48	55	25	11	38
Employed High Offense Under 27 Non-White Male	51	45	48	25	11	40
Unemployed High Offense Under 27 Non-White Male	57	46	59	33	14	47
Unemployed Low Offense Under 27 Non-White Male	59	56	56	25	5	41

Figure 8

Plot of Probability Calculations from Regression Model With Significant LSI-R and Four-way Interaction Terms Predicting New Violation Within One Year Using Individual LSI-R Means, Probability Using Mean LSI-R Means, Mean Offense, Mean LSI-R, Maximum LSI-R, and Minimum LSI-R Rank Ordered on Logistic Regression Probability

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Summary of Findings

The results from the analysis of interactions between criminal history, age, race, gender, and employment reveal that there is a considerable heterogeneity in the data due to differences in the way these variables are related to new offenses. The heterogeneity is revealed by interactions that are significant in two, three, and four way combinations of terms.

Older white female offenders had lower recidivism rates than white female offenders under 27, but older non-white female offenders did not have substantially lower recidivism rates than non-white female offenders who were under 27. Both white and non-white older female offenders experienced lower recidivism rates and more benefit from employment than female offenders under 27.

There was a notable difference in recidivism rates with respect to employment for both younger and older low offense level non-white males, who recidivate at rates comparable to low offense white offenders when employed, but recidivate at much higher rates when unemployed. This is inconsistent with previous results that indicate that there is a smaller difference in recidivism rates for non-white offenders. The problem with the previous results may be that they did not measure recidivism for separate risk and race groups.

The high offense offenders had a much smaller difference in recidivism between employed and unemployed offenders. The overall differences between male and female offenders were also noticeable. Female offenders appear to receive little benefit from employment in reducing recidivism, and non-white female offenders appear to actually recidivate more when employed. Some caution must be used when interpreting this result, as the offender counts were low in these demographic categories.

Conclusions

Hypothesis 6, suggesting that results for each category will be additive, is not supported. The results from this study indicate that interactions between age, race, gender, and previous offense level all have a substantial impact on whether employment is a protective factor in reducing recidivism rates. The fact that high offense offenders had a much smaller difference in recidivism between employed and unemployed offenders lends partial support to the low self-control hypothesis of Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990), as offenders with lower self control, as indicated by the number of previous offenses, received less of a benefit from employment.

The substantial spread in recidivism rates for low offense offenders of different races when they are unemployed provides support for strain theory, since the much higher recidivism rate for unemployed non-white males may indicate an inability to achieve valued goals, such as employment, causing strain for this population group. Pager (2003) has shown that black job applicants with a criminal record are much less likely to be hired than white applicants. This would create more strain for unemployed non-white applicants.

This study also supports the feminist claim that male and female offenders have different needs, since employment is much less beneficial for females than males. Further research must take this fact into account when reporting results.

Study Limitations

Although the overall sample size was quite large, the majority of the offenders were younger and male. This lead to some question as to whether the results were due to exogenous factors in the data for older and female offenders, where category counts were quite small. This was a descriptive study with no experimental controls, so there is no way of determining whether

the offenders had unobserved differences between categories. Also, the dependent variable, new offense, is composed of both probation violations and arrests. Probation violations are at the discretion of the probation officer and so are very subjective in nature.

Recommendations for Future Research

Future research needs to be done with a larger dataset that has more offenders in the older and female portions of the dataset. Research also needs to be done to determine what is producing the interaction effects found in the data. Why do some female offenders have a higher probation violation rate when they are employed than unemployed? Why in the recidivism rate for unemployed non-white male offenders so much higher than the recidivism rate for non-white employed offenders? Why are there such significant differences between offender groups? These and other questions should be answered.

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APPENDIX 1

Table 8

Mean LSI-R Values for Calculating Logistic Regression Probabilities

Line	Institution	Educ. Empl.	Fin. Prob.	Family Marital	Accom.	Leisure Rec.	Comp.	Alcohol Drug	Emotional Personal	Attitude Orient.
1	.722	1.444	.576	1.036	.381	.934	1.563	3.146	1.460	.695
2	1.358	2.263	.779	1.238	.513	1.108	1.871	4.371	1.842	1.238
3	1.234	5.971	1.190	1.723	.898	1.642	2.182	4.321	2.168	1.650
4	1.592	6.122	1.296	1.709	1.133	1.684	2.316	5.291	2.117	2.000
5	.592	1.803	.974	1.447	.605	.987	1.316	2.526	2.013	.605
6	1.027	2.378	1.108	1.351	.432	1.027	1.730	3.946	2.324	1.378
7	.706	5.843	1.569	1.941	.745	1.412	1.745	2.980	2.588	.588
8	1.688	6.031	1.625	2.281	.969	1.313	2.031	3.625	2.938	1.250
9	.639	.918	.525	1.336	.296	.879	1.100	2.621	1.675	.593
10	1.377	1.756	.813	1.698	.473	1.044	1.633	4.129	2.123	1.238
11	.747	4.663	1.358	1.505	.716	1.316	1.537	3.674	2.347	.979
12	1.654	5.589	1.489	2.003	.991	1.514	2.103	5.389	2.445	1.791
13	.451	1.078	.922	1.637	.382	.824	.922	2.598	2.088	.324
14	1.148	1.716	1.160	1.877	.605	1.049	1.593	3.654	2.407	1.099
15	.491	4.964	1.582	1.782	.582	1.145	1.327	4.073	2.927	.636
16	1.354	5.671	1.747	2.228	1.000	1.228	1.987	4.911	2.962	1.468
17	.917	2.000	.917	.958	.417	1.000	1.417	2.750	1.333	.583
18	1.857	3.476	.952	1.667	1.143	1.381	1.905	4.095	1.905	1.762
19	1.118	6.559	1.118	1.941	.912	1.618	2.029	3.706	1.265	1.853
20	1.878	6.817	1.341	2.012	1.451	1.841	2.756	4.793	1.915	2.524
21	1.143	2.143	1.286	1.857	.429	1.000	1.714	2.429	2.714	.286
22	1.600	3.000	1.600	2.800	1.000	1.200	2.200	2.600	2.800	.600
23	.857	6.286	2.000	2.000	.714	1.143	1.143	1.714	2.143	.286
24	1.727	6.091	1.545	2.909	1.364	1.636	2.455	3.818	2.727	2.000
25	.638	.957	.681	1.298	.489	.915	.894	1.894	1.426	.723
26	1.524	2.619	1.105	1.924	.848	1.200	1.962	4.171	2.067	1.552
27	1.045	5.227	1.455	2.227	1.545	1.500	1.909	4.227	1.682	1.182
28	1.981	5.968	1.513	2.071	1.468	1.630	2.273	5.325	2.240	2.390
29	.600	1.933	1.333	1.667	.533	.800	1.400	1.400	1.800	.533
30	1.529	2.588	1.529	2.176	.941	1.294	1.882	4.765	3.059	1.941
31	.833	5.833	1.667	2.417	.500	1.333	1.583	4.833	3.333	1.417
32	1.783	6.304	1.870	2.826	1.261	1.609	2.478	5.174	2.783	2.565
Total Mean	1.212	3.378	1.058	1.661	0.712	1.222	1.761	4.025	2.082	1.286
S.D.	0.98	2.60	0.75	1.23	0.94	0.81	1.23	2.79	1.40	1.44

Table 9

Table for LSI-R Means Showing Values Used on Each Line

Line	History	Under27	White	Male	Employed
1	0	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	1	1	1
3	0	1	1	1	0
4	1	1	1	1	0
5	0	1	1	0	1
6	1	1	1	0	1
7	0	1	1	0	0
8	1	1	1	0	0
9	0	0	1	1	1
10	1	0	1	1	1
11	0	0	1	1	0
12	1	0	1	1	0
13	0	0	1	0	1
14	1	0	1	0	1
15	0	0	1	0	0
16	1	0	1	0	0
17	0	1	0	1	1
18	1	1	0	1	1
19	0	1	0	1	0
20	1	1	0	1	0
21	0	1	0	0	1
22	1	1	0	0	1
23	0	1	0	0	0
24	1	1	0	0	0
25	0	0	0	1	1
26	1	0	0	1	1
27	0	0	0	1	0
28	1	0	0	1	0
29	0	0	0	0	1
30	1	0	0	0	1
31	0	0	0	0	0
32	1	0	0	0	0